

A New Model to describe Negative Emotions

Thilo Tscharmi

A new model to describe negative emotions is proposed. The emotion model is based on a single emotion UE which is experienced bodily by individuals. Physical detectors and eight logical detectors activate the UE in an automatic fashion in the individual. The logical detectors are activated through clearly defined and for the individual potentially unfavourable or dangerous circumstances such as missing an important goal, threat, disrespect, disadvantage, reduced health, adverse behaviours, or aversive objects. Their signals shape the negative emotions. The unpleasant UE and automatic thoughts urge the individual to an appropriate behaviour. The presented model can be consistently explained from an evolutionary perspective. Together with a similar model for positive emotions the description of all emotions is enabled. Both models explain various psychological phenomena (e.g. the fundamental attribution error) and improve the understanding, the analysis, and the explanation of emotions substantially.

1. Introduction

Various emotion theories have been proposed so far [Meyer, 2001; Meyer, 2003; Reisenzein, 2003]. These theories deal with fundamental questions concerning the when, the why and the how of the activation of emotions. They are often based on historically grown terms of emotions such as fear, anger, joy, disgust, sadness, or surprise.

In the course of time people have coined a lot of different terms for feelings and emotions. The designations for feelings in the sense of primarily physical sensations revolve around the *quality* (e.g. the itch, the pain, the feeling of pressure, the feeling of coldness) or around the *location* of their appearance (e.g. the headache, the toothache, the aching muscles, the feeling of fullness, the pins and needles in the foot). Interestingly, the designations for feelings in the sense of emotions do not revolve around different qualities or places on the body but primarily around the *situation* in which the emotion appears (e.g. jealousy, homesickness, envy, pride, separation anxiety, fright, mourning), the *actual attitude of mind* (e.g. confidence, gratitude, hatred, despair, fear, anger), and the *intensity* (e.g. worry, fear, horror, panic). This is a first indication that emotions obviously appear only in a small number of qualities (otherwise different names for different qualities of emotions would exist) but in a huge

number of different situations. Furthermore, emotions are obviously felt only in a small number of areas of the body. Besides, the historically grown terms of emotions are often not clearly defined what complicates the precise dealing with the latter [Salovey, 1984]. Most people agree that emotions appear in two basic qualities: emotions are either pleasant or unpleasant. Thus positive emotions are distinguished from negative ones. Already Aristotle distinguished those two qualities and realized that emotions base on cognition, i.e. on processes of perception and recognition [Aristotle, 350]. Also Spinoza systematically classified terms for emotions into those two basic classes and defined them appropriately [Spinoza, 1677]. Locke and Leibniz held similar views [Locke, 1690]. The following thoughts on the description and classification of negative emotions are not based on the ubiquitous terms of emotions. Instead the proposed model is based on the elementary uneasiness emotion UE. This UE, the common denominator of all negative emotions, can be bodily experienced by the perceiving individual. Eight discrete and precisely defined mechanisms, working as logical detectors, activate the elementary emotion UE automatically on a cognitive basis. The signals from those logical detectors are the foundation of negative emotions.

2. Uneasiness emotion UE

Negative emotions (such as hunger, hatred, or fear) have a common denominator [Tscharmi, 2017; Tscharmi, 2019a; Tscharmi, 2019b; Tscharmi, 2019c]. The latter is an unpleasant inner uneasiness which is called uneasiness emotion or UE in the following. It develops typically in a palm-sized area around the navel or a little above that. Indeed this is the same kind of (unexplainable) tummy-ache, which schoolchildren complain about at the paediatrician and which they get before they receive their final grades.

The UE is a (highly) unpleasant feeling. This unpleasant and disturbing character of the UE motivates (or even forces) the individual to act quickly and appropriately. Such an action brings the UE to vanish. The individual is motivated (or even forced) by the UE to fulfil a specific need situation. For example, if the UE develops because of hunger the individual is motivated or forced to search for and ingest food.

The UE represents the most central and most universal feeling of human beings. Different triggers (or occurrences) activate the UE. Those detectors can be divided into two groups: simple UE triggers and cognitive UE triggers. Simple UE triggers activate the UE according to a certain body state (e.g. hunger, urgent need to empty the bowels, nausea). Simple UE triggers are directly based on signals from physical receptors which are specialized to measure those body states. Cognitive UE triggers activate the UE by means of purely logical detection. The UE then signals a higher processed occurrence (e.g. the resentment of a different individual). Cognitive UE triggers base on indirectly derived information from already otherwise existing signals (e.g. from visual information, acoustic information). Regardless how different the UE triggers (or detectors) are, they always activate one and the same, equally felt uneasiness emotion UE.

The UE initiates or accelerates things (e.g. a behaviour). The UE has an effect like a catalyst on an appropriate behaviour. This holds for simple UE triggers as well as for cognitive UE triggers.

Beside those UE triggers (or detectors) there is another – possibly dysfunctional – way to activate the UE. The latter develops as an undetermined UE (undetermined means that the individual can not recognize a cause of the appearing UE) and often lasts for a longer time (i.e. days, even weeks). Thus the undetermined UE is not activated as usual by a specific simple or cognitive UE trigger (or detector). An undetermined UE appears during blues times or during depression (it is then also called a free-floating anxiety). The reason for the development of an undetermined UE are possibly biochemical processes in the body that got out of balance. For sure medication can activate an undetermined UE. That indicates that the undetermined UE belongs into the group of the simple UE impulses. Usually the undetermined UE vanishes after a couple of days.

The activation of positive emotions works in a similar way [Tscharmi, 2019b]. They also have a common denominator, the good emotion GE. The latter is experienced bodily in the head, peripheral below the brain skull. The intensity of the GE is much lower than the one of the UE though. The pleasant GE rewards the individual for a specific behaviour which is advantageous for it (or for its genes). Besides, the GE is a “promise for the future”: it motivates the individual to repeat a certain behaviour in the future in order to experience the pleasant GE again (this can be seen very well in the human addiction behaviour). The GE is also activated by simple GE triggers (based on information of specific physical receptors) or by cognitive GE triggers (based on logical detection).

According to their elementary importance in the experience of emotions, the UE and the GE are called elementary emotions in the following. They make it easy to distinguish emotions from other feelings (such as itch, shiver, or toothache).

3. Delimitation of terms: feelings, emotions, and thoughts

Various information appears in the consciousness of an individual. This information can be grouped into three categories: sensory impressions from specialized sensors of the body (e.g. the vision, the hearing), feelings (i.e. information that is experienced bodily), and thoughts. The first two categories overlap and form a common intersection.

The first category comprises the sensory impressions. Sensory impressions shall include all information which comes from specialized *physical* sensors or receptors that were developed by nature to provide a specific sensory impression (e.g. the hearing, the vision, the pain, the hunger). Two classes of sensory impressions can be distinguished: unfeeling sensory impressions (USI) and feeling-based sensory impressions (FSI).

Unfeeling sensory impressions (USI) comprise all information (that appears in the consciousness) which comes from physical sensors (receptors) of the body and which can't be felt. Examples for this group include the vision, the hearing, the sense of smell, the sense of taste, and the knowledge about the spatial position of the body. All of those impressions are based on signals from physical receptors which developed during evolution to generate precisely the corresponding impression. The information of those physical receptors is fed on a relatively direct way into the consciousness of the individual. Together with those information (e.g. with visual information) often an implicit understanding (i.e. without additional emotions or thoughts) of those information appears. For example, if a person sees

something then he or she sees not only the specific scene (which consists for example of three objects) but recognizes at the same time those objects and knows automatically (or implicitly) that he or she sees a table and a chair, that a table can't fly (unlike the bird, the third object, that flies through the scene at this moment) and that all this happens on his or her terrace that he or she just has walked on. Only if something in the scene is unfamiliar then the attention of the individual is immediately and automatically directed to that specific unfamiliar object (this process is called surprise) and perhaps automatic thoughts appear in addition.

The second category comprises the feelings. The category of the feelings and the category of the sensory impressions have a common intersection (the FSI). As their name indicates feelings describe bodily perceptible information. It is part of their nature that acute feelings are bound to specific locations of the body. The category of the feelings splits into the classes of the feeling-based sensory impressions without elementary emotions (FSW), the emotions, and the seeming symptoms (SSY).

The feeling-based sensory impressions without elementary emotions (FSW) comprise all sensory impressions which come from physical sensors (receptors) of the body, which can be felt, but which are no elementary emotions. The FSW include almost all of the various body sensations, such as the pain, the touch, the itch, the tickling feeling, the pinch, the burn, the shiver, the stronger trembling, the feeling of cold, the feeling of warmth, aching muscles, the feebleness, the thirst, or the pressure sense. None of those feelings is necessarily accompanied by an elementary emotion. As already mentioned, those feelings are felt in a specific, smaller or larger region of the body: typically precisely there where the attention of the individual shall be directed to¹. The kind of appearance (or quality) of the feeling often provides an indication for the individual which receptor is active and what the purpose of this receptor is. For example, an injury typically triggers pain at the corresponding place on the body. On the other hand the itch is a signal to the individual to rub (for example with its hand) the itching place on the body in order to remove a body-different (e.g. a creature, a foreign body) or a body-owned object (e.g. a scale, an eyelash). Thus a feeling of the FSW class can typically appear at various places on the body.

The second class of feelings comprises the emotions. All feelings which necessarily activate an elementary emotion (the UE or GE) are denoted by the term “emotion” in the following. That means that an emotion always activates an elementary emotion (or both elementary emotions). Emotions clearly differ from feelings of the FSW class under this aspect. The class of the emotions splits into two groups. The first group, the simple impulses SIP, still has a complete common intersection with the category of the sensory impressions and bases on signals from physical receptors that are specialized to measure the indicated parameters. The second group however, the cognitive impulses CIP, no longer has an intersection with the category of the sensory impressions and bases on a purely cognitive detection.

The simple impulses (SIP) comprise those sensory impressions which activate one or both elementary emotions (UE, GE). Thus the SIP are activated by signals from physical receptors of the body, are experienced as feelings by the individual, and always activate at least one elementary emotion. As mentioned, feelings from the FSW class indicate a certain fact (e.g. an injury) at various possible places on the body. In contrary to that, feelings from the SIP group indicate various possible facts always at one and the same place on the body (e.g.

¹ An exception is the transferred pain which is perceived on a different place on the body than its place of origin. The activation of a receptor in visceral organs for example is typically perceived as if the pain would come from the skin or from the skeleton muscles.

around the navel or a little above that in case of the UE). Simple impulses are coupled to changing body states and appear often together with other feelings (from the FSW class). Examples for simple UE impulses are the hunger (possibly the origin of all emotions), the urgent need to empty the bowels, the falling (the acceleration of the body respectively), the sexual drive, the feeling of fullness, and the nausea. Examples for simple GE impulses are the ingestion, the bowel movement, the sexual activity, and the orgasm. The interaction of simple UE- and simple GE-impulses directs the individual to a desirable behaviour. For example, hunger motivates the individual to search for food. As soon as it finds food and ingests it, the UE vanishes and the ingestion induces a GE – which rewards the individual for finding food and for the ingestion and motivates it to a similar behaviour in the future. A comparable situation arises in case of an urgent need to empty the bowels. The unpleasant UE motivates the individual to search a suitable place for defecation. During the defecation an unpleasant defecation-UE motivates the individual to proceed whereas a GE rewards the individual for the continuing bowel movement. After the defecation the unpleasant UE has gone. Also in the sexual behaviour an unpleasant UE (often termed as a drive) forces the (male) individual to sexual activity. The UE and increasing positive feelings (GE) motivate the individual to proceed with the activity and strong positive emotions during the orgasm reward for the ejaculation. The interaction of simple UE- and GE-impulses thus signals the individual how to behave in specific situations.

The elementary emotions UE and GE can therefore be understood as two feelings which can be used universally, i.e. which can be (and are) used to signal completely different facts and occurrences.

The FSW class and the SIP group form together the already mentioned intersection between the category of the sensory impressions and the category of the feelings. Contrary to this, the second group of the emotions has no intersection with the sensory impressions anymore. It comprises the cognitive impulses (CIP), i.e. the cognitive UE- and GE-impulses. In contrary to the SIP none of the cognitive impulses is based directly on information from physical receptors (or sensors). Cognitive impulses base on information from *logical* detectors instead. That means that the activation of the UE and the GE is based on pure information processing (of already existing information, for example from the USI class) and not primarily on the sensory measurement of certain parameters (like temperature or pressure). The difference between the sensory impressions and the cognitive impulses can also be depicted in an analogy to the computer world such that the sensory impressions correspond to information from hardware sensors whereas the cognitive impulses correspond to information from pure software sensors. Thus, the cognitive impulses are activated by logical detectors, are experienced as feelings by the individual, and always consist of one elementary emotion. There are eight different cognitive UE impulses (e.g. ITNOUT, SOTINA, NESPECT) and eight different cognitive GE impulses (e.g. ITWOUT, NOTINA, RESPECT). They detect and signal a specific occurrence to the individual automatically, for example an insult or a theft attempt. Cognitive impulses form the building blocks of which almost all emotions are composed. Examples for the latter include jealousy, nostalgia, sadness, fear (denotes the UE paired with the impression of inferiority), anger (denotes the UE paired with the impression of superiority), impatience, frustration, disappointment, disgust, resentment, hatred, greed, grief, shame, separation anxiety, fear of heights, wanderlust, happiness, thankfulness, elation, confidence, proud, love, and many more. Emotions based on cognitive UE impulses are remarkable phenomena since they are able to generate even strong feelings in the individual without the necessity of a simultaneous activation of any physical sensor (or receptor).

Combinations of simple (SIP) and cognitive (CIP) impulses can lead individuals to desirable behaviour too. For example, the unpleasant and painful UE resulting from (or indicating) hunger drives the new-born to cry. This crying developed such an unpleasant character during evolution that mothers react quickly to it also in order to stop that unpleasant and annoying crying. Then the feeding and the sucking evoke a GE in the child and in the mother rewarding the care of the mother and strengthening the attachment between the two individuals.

The third class of feelings consists of the seeming symptoms (SSY). Seeming symptoms denote feelings that indicate injuries, disorders, or sensations (similar to those of the FSW class) although these do not or no more correspond with the real state of the body. Seeming symptoms include for example the phantom pain, i.e. a real pain in a part of the body that has been amputated (and thus is actually not there anymore). They also include feelings resulting from the injury of an organ although this organ has already been successfully operated (and thus such feelings actually have no physical reason to occur anymore). Also sensations without an activation of the corresponding physical receptors fall into this category (for example a shudder during a horror film at the cinema (provided the cinema is heated well enough)).

The third category of information which appears in the consciousness are thoughts. Thoughts denote all information appearing in the consciousness of an individual that is neither a sensory impression nor a feeling. Thoughts appear in visual or in linguistic form in humans. At least thoughts in the form of pictures are not restricted to human beings. Two classes of thoughts can be distinguished: automatic thoughts (AT) and voluntary thoughts (VT). Many thoughts appear automatically, i.e. without any active effort, in the consciousness of the perceiving individual (the so-called automatic thoughts) [Beck, 1976]. Automatic thoughts also include dreams during sleeping. On the other hand, if a person formulates a certain content consciously and deliberately (for example the sentence “Now I am thinking deliberately.”) only in his or her mind without saying it, then a voluntary thought is created. Voluntary thoughts are very special because they enable the individual to produce and to form the impression itself that appears in its consciousness.

All information which appears in the consciousness of an individual can be depicted as a cake with the seven succeeding pieces USI, FSW, SIP, CIP, SSY, AT, and VT.

4. UE impulses

4.1 Simple UE impulses

Simple UE triggers (or detectors) activate the elementary emotion UE directly through signals about the state of the body which are delivered by physical receptors (or sensors respectively) which are specialized to measure those body states. Examples for simple UE impulses include the hunger, the urgent need to empty the bowels, the falling (the acceleration of the body, respectively), the sexual drive (positive emotions arise here too), the feeling of fullness, and the nausea. All those body states activate the unpleasant elementary emotion UE automatically. This happens through signals from specialized receptors which monitor the body state. For example, hunger is activated in humans through a combination of signals from

different sensors of the body. Among them are stretching sensors and filling level sensors in the stomach, blood sugar-, insulin-, and free fatty acid-sensors in the hypothalamus, and various chemoreceptors. In contrast, the UE which is activated during falling is fed from signals from the organ of equilibrium in the human ear. Thus the activation of the elementary emotion UE through simple UE detectors bases on clearly defined measurable quantities. Some of the simple UE impulses appear together with other feelings (of the FSW class). For example, in case of rising hunger the UE can be accompanied by additional sensations from the area of the stomach (which is located mainly in the left half of the human body). In case of an urgent need to empty the bowels, the UE often appears together with feelings of pressure in the area of the rectum. Note that in case of two simultaneously occurring feelings the stronger one usually drowns the other. This peculiarity of the human feeling system (which pickpockets exploit) was already known in ancient times [Darwin, 1872]. The stronger feeling attracts one's attention and the individual has to scan its body voluntarily and consciously in order to perceive also the other feeling.

The activated unpleasant and disturbing UE motivates the individual to a suited behaviour (i.e. an action or an omission) which lets this unpleasant UE vanish. For example, in case of hunger the individual is motivated to search for food and ingest it. Simple UE impulses constitute the SIP group.

4.2 Cognitive UE impulses

The automatic release of the unpleasant UE through cognitive UE triggers (or detectors) is not based on specialized physical receptors (as this is the case for simple UE impulses) but on logical detection instead. Those logical detectors build on information processing or on cognitive pattern recognition of already otherwise existing information (e.g. visible, audible, stored information). Thus, the cognitive activation of the UE is based on an indirect determination of the desired parameters. The activated UE signals the individual the result of this information processing (e.g. the perception of a hindrance of an own important striving). Such an activation of a cognitive UE detector follows clearly defined rules and is coupled to the perception of a specific occurrence (e.g. the perception of a disrespect for the own personality). Therefore, the signals of UE detectors often manifest like an impulse, i.e. they appear suddenly and they are clearly perceptible. Dependent on the specific situation, the activated UE lasts then for a longer or shorter period of time.

Eight different cognitive UE impulses originating from eight different cognitive UE triggers (or UE detectors) can be distinguished: ITNOUT, SOTINA, NESPECT, HASAD, NOWEL, UDINOR, IDINOR, and DISLIKIT. They are described in detail in the following.

Occasionally cognitive UE impulses are accompanied by other feelings (e.g. of the FSW class). Cognitive UE impulses are part of the CIP group.

But first a remark to the nomenclature. All UE triggers (or detectors) activate one and the same UE. Dependent on the specific situation, this UE can appear stronger, weaker, longer, or shorter but it always appears in the same, bodily experienced, unpleasant form. In order to be able to distinguish the different signals from the different cognitive UE detectors, the former are given different names which refer to the activated UE detector (or to the reason of the activation, respectively). For example, ITNOUT denotes the UE which is activated by the

ITNOUT detector. Analogously, SOTINA denotes the UE which is activated by the SOTINA detector.

4.2.1 ITNOUT

Definition: *ITNOUT* [itnaot] (abbreviation of “*It does not work out (like I want it to)*”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of a hindrance of an own important striving.

The ITNOUT detector controls whether a real or a potential hindrance endangers a striving of the individual. If this is the case then the detector generates a warning signal in the form of the UE (ITNOUT) automatically.

This cognitive UE impulse appears very often. The automatic activation of ITNOUT requires that the perceiving individual strives for an explicit or implicit goal. This goal can be of short-term (e.g. to tie up the own shoelaces) or of long-term nature (e.g. to graduate). Striving means that the individual itself would like to achieve this goal – through its own or through someone else’s activity (i.e. through a particular action or omission). Striving bases thus on an underlying own goal of the individual. Examples for such a striving are to reach a different place, to get or ingest food, to realize an activity, to communicate with another individual, to get a certain information or object, to bring another individual or an object to a desired behaviour, or to build or destroy something. Moreover, at the current moment the individual considers it as important to reach its goal. The prerequisite for the activation of ITNOUT is thus an own striving which is important to the individual (at the current moment).

But then the individual faces a hindrance of its striving by an internal or external (i.e. different from the own body) power. This power has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the same species can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organisation). Examples for such a power include a different individual (e.g. parents, siblings, the partner, children, colleagues, drivers, officials, animals, weed), the perceiving individual itself, an inanimate object (e.g. a device, a toy, a vehicle), natural forces (e.g. the weather, gravity), or chance (e.g. coincidence).

A hindrance develops because of an unfavourable behaviour or property of the power. This negatively affects the striving of the perceiving individual. The hindrance (potentially) delays or prevents the reaching of the goal. Examples of such a hindrance include an unfavourable property or behaviour of other individuals (like badly performing collaborators, an unreliable supplier, an unwelcome interruption), an unfavourable own property or behaviour (like a gap in one’s memory, a lacking ability), an unfavourable property or behaviour of inanimate objects (like a technical or material defect, a volcanic eruption), an unfavourable property or behaviour of natural forces (like a sudden change in the weather, an unexpected consequence of gravity), an unfavourable effect of chance or coincidence (like a traffic jam, a sold out product, a closed store because of a strike), or an unfavourable property of an intellectual object (e.g. an insoluble riddle).

It is crucial for all cognitive impulses (as described in their definitions) that the individual actually perceives (or recognizes) the corresponding situation (here: a hindrance). Only under this condition a cognitive impulse can be generated. If an individual does not perceive an occurring hindrance, for example because it is distracted by something else, then no ITNOUT

impulse appears.

ITNOUT is an unpleasant emotion. The intensity of this automatically generated UE typically ranges from small to distinct. The activated UE can appear in different expressions.

Expressions denote different terms for the UE in different situations. Sometimes expressions go along with changes in physiology, body language², accompanying feelings (for example of the FSW class), or behaviour. The expression of ITNOUT is often anger; furthermore impatience, frustration, stress, sadness, or fear.

In an ITNOUT situation (i.e. a situation in which ITNOUT dominates) automatic thoughts (i.e. automatically generated thoughts) often appear in the consciousness of the individual. These automatic thoughts focus on the cause of the UE generation, i.e. on the hindrance of an own important striving which has been perceived. Such automatic thoughts are of descriptive nature (“Oh no: a garbage truck is blocking the road.”), of explaining nature (“They are always taking this route on Tuesday.”), showing possible consequences (“This is delaying my journey.”), at odds with the situation (“Why are they driving here right now?”), of blaming others nature (“Why don’t they let pass other cars?”), of self-accusing nature (“I should have chosen a different route.”), of catastrophizing character (“Now I certainly will arrive too late.”), or – seldom – of de-escalating nature (“I will arrive in time.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences.

In a UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) that is dominated by ITNOUT the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and rarely even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through).

A hindrance of the striving of an individual leads to an (emotional) behaviour [Mandler, 1964]. In and after an ITNOUT situation, individuals show different types of behaviour dependent on their abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and on the specific situation (which restricts the number of available options). Examples include to laugh about the situation, to start a similar or a different trial to overcome the obstacle, to approach the obstacle in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or an unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination)), to by-pass the hindrance, to look for an appropriate tool, to communicate with other individuals, to seek help, to cooperate with other individuals, to ignore the obstacle, to give up its striving, or to wait until or if the obstacle disappears by its own. After the obstacle has disappeared the individual can try to make up for the disadvantage suffered (e.g. to make up for the lost time), or change its behaviour in order to prevent similar ITNOUT experiences in the future.

Human behaviour is goal-directed [Srull, 1986]. A hindrance to the achievement of a goal can lead to frustration. Dollard and his colleagues postulated that the higher this frustration is the higher the probability for an aggressive reaction becomes [Dollard, 1939]. This *frustration-aggression hypothesis* has been confirmed in many investigations [Berkowitz, 1998].

² Anger, fear, mourning, disgust, and joy have their own facial expressions. The latter serve the automatic display of own emotions to other people [Ekman, 2003].

4.2.2 SOTINA

Definition: *SOTINA* [səʊtama] (abbreviation of “*Somebody takes something away from me*”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of a taking away of an own significant resource.

A taking away of own resources can become dangerous for an individual. The former is thus the basis of the SOTINA detector. If a taking away is detected then a warning signal in the form of the UE (SOTINA) is raised automatically.

The prerequisite for the generation of SOTINA in an individual is the existence of an own significant resource. The term “resource” includes anything what is able to generate positive (i.e. pleasant) feelings in the perceiving individual. Such a resource has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. Such a resource can also be owned by a different individual, nevertheless the former is able to generate positive (i.e. pleasant) feelings in the perceiving individual. The resource has to be significant for the individual, i.e. the resource has to have a positive meaning for the perceiving individual. Examples for the resources of a human include a beloved partner, beloved children, possession, property, food, fortune, ability, power, the own health, hobbies, preferences, persons of public life that he likes, splendid public buildings, or of children their teddy bears or dolls. No resources are for most individuals the own garbage or enemies.

This resource is then (potentially) partly or entirely taken away from the perceiving individual. This taking away is carried out by an internal or external (i.e. different from the own body) power. This power has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the same species can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organisation). Examples for such a power are volcanic eruptions, flashes of lightning, fires, conflagrations, deep or raging waters, tsunamis, strong winds, severe cold or heat, dangerous submarine cliffs, earthquakes, avalanches, very confined caves, harmful substances, radiation, gravity, thieves, criminal organisations, war, vehicles of all kind (on a collision course), a high voltage, predators, poisonous plants or animals, huge swarms of locusts, a dangerous virus, severe diseases, senescence, or evil spirits. The classic example from the realm of SOTINA is the threat by a predator.

A generation of SOTINA requires that the individual perceives such a taking away, i.e. the reduction of its resources. If an individual does not perceive the loss of an own significant resource then no SOTINA impulse is generated (yet) – a fact that pickpockets take advantage of. Equally, if an individual falls into an ambush and does not realize the ambush then SOTINA does not appear (early enough).

The SOTINA called UE is per se unpleasant. This automatically generated UE can appear with a high intensity in the individual, i.e. very painfully [Wortman, 1987; Panksepp, 1998]. The expression (or the overall emotional manifestation) of this UE is often worry or fear; other forms include sadness, grief, mourning, longing, disappointment, frustration, stress, anger, or despair.

In a SOTINA situation (i.e. a situation in which SOTINA dominates) automatic thoughts (in the form of pictures or language) are frequently generated. Such automatic thoughts centre on the cause of the generation of the UE, i.e. on the (potential) taking away of an own significant resource [Wortman, 1987]. They are of descriptive nature (“Somebody has stolen my

laptop.”), of explaining nature (“That has certainly happened in the crush a couple of minutes ago.”), showing possible consequences (“Now I will have to produce all those documents again.”), at odds with the situation (“Why must this happen right now?”), of blaming others nature (“The thieves were certainly those strange guys that I saw a couple of minutes ago.”), of self-accusing character (“I should have been more careful.”), of catastrophizing character (“Now company secrets are possibly in danger.”), or – rarely – of de-escalating nature (“My computer has a strong password protection.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences. In a UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by SOTINA the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through). Sometimes a lack of drive occurs. A very long lasting UE phase (i.e. many weeks) is called depression. Then often an undetermined UE occurs in addition.

In and after a SOTINA situation, individuals show different types of behaviour dependent on their abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options). Examples include to approach the threat in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or an unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination)), to avoid the threat, to flee, to give up the resource (even to destroy the latter), to arm itself, to protect the resource, to make duplicates, to communicate with other individuals about the threat, to seek help, to cooperate with other individuals, to warn other individuals, to ignore the threat, to wait until or if the threat disappears by itself, to strive to get back the resource or to acquire a similar one, or to take revenge. An individual often tries to avoid such a taking away in the future. A seldom reaction to severe threat or loss situations – especially in a seemingly hopeless situation – is to commit suicide. The impression of hopelessness, i.e. the perceived lack of a way out, is a key factor in the decision of an individual to commit suicide [Beck, 1975; Dyer, 1984; Salter, 1990].

The high intensity of SOTINA in case of losses leads humans to avoid losses. It can be demonstrated that humans show a *loss aversion*. They assess losses higher than gains of equal size [Kahneman, 1984].

To complete the picture it shall be mentioned that beside the SOTINA generation just described there exists in humans and animals a second, rudimentary cognitive generation of the UE in case of a potential or real danger. In order to increase the speed of reaction in such a situation, a generation of the UE already sets in *before* the cognitive process of recognition has been completed. To be on the safe side, a premature alarm is set off. This is for example the case if an object very quickly approaches the perceiving individual. If the individual perceives such a quickly approaching object, then a clear UE impulse, a leading of its attention to this object, and even an automatic flight reaction can be generated. This very fast reaction increases the chance of survival of the individual on average (for example in case of a real attack of a predator) even though in many cases a too quick generation of the UE turns out to be a false alarm. The latter occurs because a premature raise of an alarm goes inherently along with a higher probability of false alarms. Another example is to get a fright. Such a startle reflex occurs in situations in which the individual perceives a sudden, a strong, or an unusual sensory impression which potentially could be dangerous (e.g. a sudden touch, a

sudden loud noise, a strange noise, or a sudden electric shock). This short cut in setting off an alarm has been neurologically described and proved by the brain researcher LeDoux [LeDoux, 1996].

4.2.3 NESPECT

Definition: *NESPECT* [nispekt] (*abbreviation of “I am not respected”*) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of a *disrespect for the own personality*.

A disrespect for the own personality can become dangerous for an individual. The former constitutes thus the basis of the NESPECT detector. If such a disrespect is detected then a warning signal in the form of the UE (NESPECT) is activated automatically.

The centre of this cognitive UE impulse is the very own part of any individual: the own personality. The personality of an individual includes all characteristics which make it out as a living being. The structure of the personality can be divided into four components: into the physical structure (e.g. the look, the age, the constitution, the health), the intellectual structure (e.g. the knowledge, the intelligence, the mental processes), the own values (e.g. the wishes, the will, the values of the individual value system, its opinions, its expectations), and the behaviour (e.g. the doing, the disposition, the temperament, the achievements, the acquisitions).

The own personality is then treated disrespectfully by an external (i.e. different from the own body) power. This power is virtually always a part of the living world, i.e. the disrespect is coming from one or several individuals of the same species or of a different species. These individuals are often directly associated with the life of the perceiving individual. Examples for such a power include class-mates, colleagues, superiors, partners, the husband, the wife, children, siblings, parents, relatives, neighbours, sellers, doormen, politicians, a dog which is barking at the perceiving individual, stalkers, or rapists. The classic example from the realm of NESPECT is the threat by a dominant conspecific.

The disrespect takes place in a verbal, non-verbal, or physical form. Humans react highly sensitive to such signals. Some of those signals are dependent on culture, others are understandable independent of the culture or the species (e.g. to yell at somebody, to physically attack somebody). There is a multitude of gestures of disrespect which has to be learned by a (young) individual. A widely known gesture is “the finger”, i.e. the extended middle finger, which is shown to an individual with the back of the hand towards it. This gesture is one of the oldest known insults and was already well known in the ancient Rome as “*digitus impudicus*” (indecent finger). Another widespread gesture of disrespect is the repeated tapping – with the forefinger – to the temple or to the forehead. This gesture shall indicate that the other individual has a malfunctioning brain. However, for this gesture the context is important: precisely the same gesture can also mean that the other individual is clever. Other forms of behaviour are normal in one culture but not in another. For example, in the Middle East and the Orient it is a severe offence if somebody sits and puts a foot onto its other knee such that the sole of the shoe points to another person. Such a behaviour can have severe consequences for the individual [Morris, 1994].

Four different kinds of disrespect can be distinguished. The most obvious kind is the *direct or indirect attack* on the perceiving individual. Another kind is a *lack of attention* or even the ignoring of the perceiving individual. A third form is a *false interest* where the perceiving individual is made the centre of attention but without any true interest in its personality (e.g.

just for the purpose of an amusement of other people). And the fourth kind is an *unwelcomed* (although true) *interest*, for example from an obstinate but unwelcomed admirer.

In an experiment from Eisenberger, subjects were invited to a virtual ball-tossing game called Cyberball. Each participant played on a computer against two other subjects who were located in different rooms. The three participants could toss a ball to each other on the computer just as they liked. After a few tosses the other two subjects suddenly began to toss the ball merely to each other – the first participant was excluded from the game by them. He or she suffered a substantial painful UE from this social exclusion. What the participant didn't know: he or she didn't play against two other subjects but merely against a simple computer program [Eisenberger, 2003]. The experiment shows that the disrespect itself is crucial for the activation of NESPECT and less from which individual it comes. Baumeister and Tice suppose that the mechanism which is activating NESPECT in case of social exclusion is of innate origin [Baumeister, 1990].

A generation of an automatic NESPECT impulse requires that the individual perceives the disrespect for him or her. If the individual does not perceive the disrespect then no NESPECT impulse is activated. The latter can be observed with small children: they still lack a sense of shame because they don't yet realize that they are laughed at or jeered at for a certain behaviour from older individuals and that the amusement of the bystanders is not meant in a positive but a negative way towards them.

The NESPECT called UE is per se unpleasant. Such a UE which develops automatically because of the perception of a disrespect for the own personality can reach high intensities, i.e. it can be very painfully. In the Cyberball experiment the intensity of the activated UE equalled the one of a physical pain [Eisenberger, 2003]. The expressions (or the overall emotional manifestations) of this UE include – according to the specific situation – worry and fear respectively, disappointment, anger, shame, frustration, stress, and despair.

The automatically generated UE in such a NESPECT situation (i.e. a situation in which NESPECT prevails) is often accompanied by automatic thoughts (in the form of pictures or language). The central theme of these thoughts consists in the cause of the generation of the UE, i.e. the disrespect for the own personality that has been perceived. The content of those automatic thoughts is of descriptive nature (“This unhappy customer has quite sworn at me.”), of explaining nature (“He is waiting since a long time for a solution to his problem.”), showing possible consequences (“He threatened with dissolving the bill of sale.”), at odds with the situation (“Why is it always me who gets the difficult customers?”), of blaming others nature (“A completely boorish guy.”), of self-accusing character (“I should have de-escalated the situation better.”), of catastrophizing character (“He could call my boss and complain about me.”), or – rarely – of de-escalating nature (“He will calm down.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences.

In a UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by NESPECT the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through). Also a lack of drive may occur. A very long lasting UE phase (i.e. many weeks) is called depression. Then often an undetermined UE occurs in addition.

In and after a NESPECT situation, individuals have – dependent on their abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options) – different behavioural options. They include to approach the party which is responsible for the disrespect in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination)), to avoid the party which is responsible for the disrespect, to ignore the disrespect, to communicate with other individuals, to seek help, to warn other individuals, to cooperate with other individuals or with the originator of NESPECT, to claim an excuse, to seek for revenge, to wait until or if the disrespect comes to an end by itself, or to change its behaviour in order to prevent future NESPECT experiences. A seldom reaction to severe disrespect situations is to commit suicide (for example in the case of mobbing, in a widely visible disrespect situation, or in a seemingly hopeless situation). The impression of hopelessness, i.e. the perceived lack of a way out, is a key factor in the decision of an individual to commit suicide [Beck, 1975; Dyer, 1984; Salter, 1990].

NESPECT influences the behaviour of an individual in a group. Many individuals do within a group things that they would do differently otherwise. In order to prevent painful social vituperations and to get recognition they conform to the group, i.e. they behave like other members of the group or like they expect it to. They comply with the norms of a group. Asch demonstrated this in a simple experiment. Each participant was placed in a group of 7-9 persons and was shown large white cards with a black line on them. The length of this line had to be found again on a second card with three lines of different lengths. What the participant didn't know: all other group members were initiates of the experimenter. After a while they began unanimously and consistently to choose a wrong line on the second card – what made the participant increasingly unsure. It turned out that many participants began to match their answers to the wrong one of the other group members [Asch, 1956]. Women seem to be more affected by this behaviour of *conformity* (or group think) [Bond, 1996].

The cognitive impulse NESPECT plays an important part in the building of social hierarchies and groups. Its existence reduces the probability that conspecifics have to physically hurt each other in order to force their claims and interests. Instead the painful generation of NESPECT is often sufficient in order to clarify positions and memberships. The existence of NESPECT thus enables the substitution of physical violence for emotional violence what reduces the risk that the perceiving individual suffers physical injuries.

Furthermore, NESPECT is important in the *territoriality*. The fear of punishment often leads to a respect for the territories of other individuals. Therefore in many species mere threatening actions are sufficient in order to defend marked out territories against the neighbours [Franck, 1985]. Humans lay out their bath towels on the beach side by side and not on top of each other in order to respect the territories of others and to mark the own ones. Again it is important that an individual knows the signals which mark a territory in order to prevent unnecessary clashes.

4.2.4 HASAD

Definition: *HASAD* [hæsæd] (abbreviation of “He/she/it has an advantage”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of an advantage of a different individual regarding a resource which is also claimed by the perceiving individual.

The HASAD detector automatically compares resources of other individuals with the own ones. Undesired inequalities can activate a warning signal in the form of the UE (HASAD) automatically.

Like SOTINA this cognitive UE impulse bases on a resource. However, not the perceiving individual owns that resource but a different power has it in possession. This resource has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. Examples for such a resource are food, a toy, possessions of all kind (e.g. a watch, a device, a car), attributes (e.g. beautiful hair, intelligence), money, success, an accommodation (e.g. an apartment, a house), a mate, status symbols, power, attention of other individuals, publicity, happiness, or youthfulness.

The perceiving individual would like to own this resource, it would like to claim it as its own. This claim of ownership is of critical importance for the activation of HASAD. Already infants show such a claim [Frankel, 1977; Salovey, 1984; Rosenblatt, 1988]. Without a claim to a resource there is no activation of HASAD in the perceiving individual. The claim can also take a broader range. In case of a wedding for example it can apply to the bride (or the groom) but also to the marrying (or the being married) itself or to the youth typically involved with a marriage.

The perceiving individual automatically compares its own situation with the one of the other power. The comparability of these two situations is virtually irrelevant. That means that the HASAD detector automatically compares also individuals with each other which are very different.

However, the claimed resource is owned by a different power. This power is almost always a different individual which is almost always of the same species (rarely it is a group of individuals). Examples for such a power are siblings, classmates, colleagues, superiors, friends, neighbours, persons in public life, or prosperous individuals. The classic example from the realm of HASAD is rivalry among siblings.

Through its resource the other power has an advantage over the perceiving individual. Four different kinds of advantages can be distinguished. In case of an *absolute advantage* only the other power (but not the perceiving individual) possesses the resource. In all three other forms of advantages the perceiving individual owns a similar resource as the one of the other power. In case of a *qualitative advantage* the individual perceives a better composition of the resource of the other power (for example a faster car, a more beautiful dress) compared to its own resource. In case of a *quantitative advantage* the individual perceives a more advantageous (and often higher) quantity of the resource of the other power (for example a higher salary, a younger woman) compared to its own resource. In case of a *relative advantage* finally, the perceiving individual already possesses a qualitatively and quantitatively superior resource compared to the one of the other power, but it lays a total claim to the resource, i.e. it wants to possess as much as possible of the available resources and thus also claims a part or all of the one of the other power (e.g. a sibling who claims not only his own share of the inheritance but the complete inheritance for himself).

An activation of HASAD requires finally that an individual perceives the situation (i.e. an advantage of a different individual) before a HASAD impulse can be released automatically. Without such a preceding perception is no generation of HASAD possible.

The HASAD called UE is per se unpleasant. The intensity of this automatically generated UE typically ranges between small and distinct. Such a UE resulting from the perception of an advantage of a different power can have various expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) such as envy, frustration, anger, sadness, or wistfulness. Envy appears

worldwide [Rosenblatt, 1988].

In addition to the UE automatic thoughts typically come up in such a HASAD situation (i.e. a situation in which HASAD dominates). Their central theme is the cause of the generated UE, i.e. the perceived advantage of a different power. The content of those automatic thoughts is of descriptive nature (“My co-worker has been promoted.”), of explaining nature (“I had also hoped to get this promotion.”), showing possible consequences (“Now this job is filled for a longer time.”), at odds with the situation (“Why didn’t I get the promotion?”), of blaming others nature (“He is much worse qualified than me.”), of self-accusing nature (“I should have positioned myself more clearly.”), of catastrophizing character (“I can’t make any progress in this company.”), or – seldom – of de-escalating character (“There will be other opportunities.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the current UE generation or on its possible consequences.

If a UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by HASAD sets in, then the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), or to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE).

Individuals show different types of behaviour in and after a HASAD situation. Dependent on its abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options) an individual has different behavioural options. They include to approach the advantage or the other power in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination); e.g. it may disparage the other power, steal its resource, destroy it), to avoid the other power and its resource, (if possible) to strive for a similar or a better resource or advantage, to communicate with other individuals, to seek help (for example to complain to a higher or the allocation authority), to ignore the advantage, or to wait until or if the latter disappears by itself.

Characteristically, HASAD often appears in childhood. This is possibly the case since in childhood visible allocations are a frequent occurrence (e.g. in the parental home, on the playground, in school).

Salovey and Rodin conducted an instructive experiment with students concerning this topic. The subjects were randomly assigned to one of eight groups in which they received either positive or negative feedback on a bogus personality test that was either consistent with their own goals or not, followed by feedback of the successful performance by another person with the same or other goals as the subjects. It turned out that envy (or HASAD) occurred especially if a subject got a negative feedback in the area of his own goals and the successfully performing other person had the same goals. In those subjects thoughts appeared which focused on the superiority of the rival. These subjects tended to disparage the rival and to show less interest in a friendship with this person. They even began to hate this rival although they had never met him [Salovey, 1984].

Note that the generation of HASAD does *not* correspond to a complete sense of justice since HASAD appears merely in case of a (as unfair perceived) advantage of a different individual but never in case of an own advantage.

4.2.5 NOWEL

Definition: *NOWEL* [nɔwel] (abbreviation of “I do not feel well”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of a serious reduction of the own physical integrity.

The most valuable asset of any individual is its physical integrity, i.e. its health. This physical integrity is controlled by the NOWEL detector. If the latter detects a serious reduction of the own physical integrity, then a warning signal in the form of the UE (NOWEL) is generated automatically.

People who worry about the own health are a widespread phenomenon [Hypo, 1962]. The cognitive UE impulse NOWEL refers to the physical (including mental) integrity of the perceiving individual. NOWEL appears automatically in case of the perception of a (plausible) serious reduction of the own health level, i.e. in case of a reduction compared to the last perceived own health level (the status quo ante). Crucial for the generation of NOWEL is thus the relative but not the absolute health level. Because of this circumstance NOWEL does no longer occur after a real reduction of the own health level has been perceived by the individual (provided that the new – reduced – health level remains stable). This point is supported by many studies. For example, the happiness of people who have suffered paraplegia through an accident is similar to the one of ordinary people after a while [Brickman, 1978]. The same is true for blind people [Feinman, 1978]. Furthermore, a substantial number of studies shows that the well-being of humans primarily depends on the relative (subjective) but not on the absolute (objective) health [Diener, 1984].

The individual gains indications of a reduction of the own health level through self-observation of its body and observed conspicuousnesses or changes. Examples for the latter include physical injuries, changes of the skin, palpable lumps, visual defects, fever, or other bodily symptoms. Further indications are provided by feelings, for example pain, strange sensations, or physical weakness. But even external indications can trigger NOWEL such as laboratory results, results of an examination, opinions of experts, information from health magazines, or even the mere knowledge about the existence of a certain disease.

However, in order to trigger NOWEL there has to be an indication for a serious reduction of the own physical integrity. A graze which is classified as minor from the perceiving individual does not activate NOWEL.

A generation of NOWEL requires the individual to perceive a (real or possible) serious reduction of its physical integrity. Without such a perception no NOWEL impulse can be generated.

The NOWEL called UE is per se unpleasant. Such an automatically generated UE resulting from the perception of a serious reduction of the own health can occur with high intensity. The expression of this UE (or the overall emotional manifestation) is mainly worry or fear, seldom disappointment.

In such a NOWEL situation (i.e. a situation in which NOWEL prevails) accompanying automatic thoughts focus on the cause of the generation of the UE, i.e. on the (possible) serious reduction of the own health which has been perceived. Their contents are of descriptive nature (“What’s this strange blotch on my skin all about?”), of explaining nature (“I didn’t notice it so far.”), showing possible consequences (“It could indicate a disease.”), at odds with the situation [Janoff Bulman, 1977] (“Why me? Why now? Why this on top?”), of blaming others nature [Janoff Bulman, 1977] (“Somebody has given it to me.”), of self-

accusing nature [Janoff Bulman, 1977] (“I should have paid more attention to it.”), of catastrophizing character (“I could be seriously ill.”), or – seldom – of de-escalating character (“It will be gone until tomorrow.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences.

In a UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by NOWEL the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through). Sometimes a lack of drive occurs.

In and after a NOWEL situation, an individual shows – dependent on its abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options) – different kinds of behaviour. They include to wait and observe how things develop, to treat itself by its own means (for example to disinfect a wound), to seek and take an appropriate medicine, to seek medical information or a medical specialist, to communicate with other individuals about the problem, to ignore the NOWEL impulse, or to strive to improve its physical integrity. Sometimes an individual changes its behaviour in order to prevent similar NOWEL experiences in the future (e.g. by taking precautions against a certain disease).

It is typical for a NOWEL situation that the automatic thoughts focus on the worst conceivable cause of the perceived symptoms – despite the fact that a certain symptom often has a multitude of also harmless possible causes. The philosopher Immanuel Kant wrote that in his younger years such disturbing thoughts and feelings “verged on the satiety of life” [Kant, 1798]. Studies show that in NOWEL situations worries about the own health prevail and worst case thoughts (e.g. to have a serious disease, imminent death) appear often [Kellner, 1987].

If a person gets an all-clear for his or her health worries which is plausible for himself or herself then NOWEL disappears suddenly. Such an all-clear can come from an expert (for example from a medical doctor, from the mother in case of children), from specialist literature, or from another plausible source.

As mentioned, NOWEL also vanishes after the perception of a real reduction of the own physical integrity. This is different to other cognitive UE impulses: the UE vanishes although the underlying problem for the generation of NOWEL still persists. This limitation of the generation of NOWEL to the relative health level (instead to the absolute health level) makes sense and serves the protection of the individual. In case of a permanent reduction of the health or in case of an illness a continually active NOWEL alarm signal would be counter-productive or even harmful for the individual.

4.2.6 UDINOR

Definition: *UDINOR* [ju:damər] (abbreviation of “*You did something not right*”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of an inappropriate behaviour of a different power.

The behaviour (or the property) of other individuals or of inanimate objects can have an adverse effect on an individual. In case of such an inappropriate behaviour, the UDINOR detector activates a warning signal in the form of the UE (UDINOR) automatically. UDINOR appears very frequently. This cognitive UE impulse refers to a different power. This power has a material or immaterial consistence. It is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. It can be a single individual, a group of individuals, or an organization. Examples for such a power are a mobbing colleague, a whining child, an annoying fly, or a bad tennis racket.

This power shows a behaviour, i.e. an action or an omission, which is automatically classified as inappropriate by the perceiving individual. An inappropriate behaviour is a (intentional or unintentional) behaviour which evokes an unwanted unpleasant feeling in the perceiving individual (for example a UE or a pain) or which violates the opinions of the perceiving individual. Examples for such an inappropriate behaviour of a different power are insults, to be barked at by a dog, a poor performance of the favourite soccer club, or a spell of bad weather during holidays. Thus often a different cognitive UE impulse (for example ITNOUT, NESPECT, DISLIKIT) precedes the generation of UDINOR. Nevertheless, UDINOR can also appear independently, i.e. without a preceding negative feeling.

As described in the definition, an automatic generation of UDINOR requires that the individual actually perceives that a different power is responsible for an own negative feeling or a bad situation. If this perception lacks then no UDINOR impulse is generated.

The UDINOR called UE is per se unpleasant. The intensity of this UE ranges from small to strong [Frijda, 1994]. The expression (or the overall emotional manifestation) of this UE is mainly anger, sometimes stress, or frustration.

In a UDINOR situation (i.e. a situation in which UDINOR dominates) typically automatically generated thoughts (i.e. automatic thoughts) appear in the consciousness of the individual. They refer to the cause of the generation of UDINOR, for example to a mistake of a different individual, i.e. to an inappropriate behaviour of the other power that has been perceived automatically. Their contents are of descriptive nature (“Now my interlocutor could show up.”), of explaining nature (“I have been waiting for twenty minutes for him.”), showing possible consequences (“That delay could affect my succeeding appointments.”), at odds with the situation (“Why isn’t he more punctual?”), of (also pejoratively) blaming others nature (“He is never on time.”), of self-accusing character (“Why didn’t I notice his weakness of character earlier?”), of catastrophizing character (“Because of him I will miss my lunch or be late at an important following meeting.”), or – rarely – of de-escalating character (“He will certainly arrive soon.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences.

In case of a succeeding UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by UDINOR the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through). Often a push in energy appears.

Typical for UDINOR is an accompanying urge for a (pejorative) rebuke (through criticism, insult, threat) for the other power. Such a rebuke takes place in verbal, non-verbal or physical form. Equally typical is the simultaneously developing impression in the perceiving

individual to be absolutely right in the current situation and thus to have the right or even the duty to utter such a rebuke. The individual might even feel especially alive in such a UDINOR situation. This increases its impression further to be the one who is right. Such a pejorative rebuke can be prevented by means of impulse control (and deliberate thoughts). In and after a UDINOR situation, an individual can act in different ways dependent on its abilities (e.g. its knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which restricts the number of available options). These include to approach the other power in an unfriendly way – a typical kind of behaviour in a UDINOR situation – (verbally (e.g. to shout at somebody), non-verbally (e.g. to threaten somebody), physically (including elimination)), to approach the other power in a friendly manner (verbally, non-verbally, physically), to avoid the other power, to seek help, to communicate with other individuals about the perceived misbehaviour, to warn other individuals, to ignore the UDINOR impulse, to calm things down and for example excuse itself (e.g. for an own overreaction), or to punish the other individual (e.g. to show an act of defiance, to get into a huff). A seldom reaction to a severe inappropriate behaviour of a different power is to commit suicide (e.g. among adolescents intending to punish other individuals; to burn oneself to death).

UDINOR often leads to an unfriendly approach to the other power. Verbal forms of such an unfriendly approach include the reproach, the scolding, the making a noise (e.g. the crying), the insult, and the threat. Also non-verbally, i.e. through body language, the perceiving individual has a wide range of aggressive forms of expression at its disposal. Those include the making a noise (e.g. the drumming, the sounding the horn), the planting itself in front of the other power, the approach, the change of the facial expression (e.g. to pull together the eyebrows, to show the teeth), the gestures of insult (as mentioned in the NESPECT section), and the gestures of threat. The most common threatening gesture worldwide is the shaking of the fist towards the opponent. Another worldwide gesture consists in the threat with the extended index finger. The latter moves repeatedly downwards in the direction of the other power (what symbolizes a beating). Also the pointing one's finger at the opponent can be a worldwide well-known threatening gesture [Morris, 1994]. Further non-verbal aggressive forms of expression are the disparaging waving aside, the irritated turning away, and the demonstrative ignoring (e.g. in defiance). Physical forms of an unfriendly approach are among others the throwing an object at the other power, the shoving, the beating, the kicking, the injuring (e.g. through scratching, biting), and the elimination. In a UDINOR situation, the different levels of escalation often follow very quickly on each other or are even skipped. Thoughts and behaviour in a UDINOR situation are fuelled by two main purposes. The first purpose is to *motivate* the other power to change its inappropriate behaviour in the future. Such a change would improve the living conditions of the perceiving individual and reduce the number of unpleasant UE generations. The second purpose (e.g. if the first one is not feasible) is to *punish* the other power for its inappropriate behaviour and for the painful UE suffered. The suffering shall be equalized [Frijda, 1994]. A “successful” punishment can also motivate the other individual to change its behaviour. Both purposes require a boost in energy, self-confidence, and motivation in the perceiving individual in order to have a chance to be successful.

Note that the automatic assignment of the responsibility for such an inappropriate behaviour to a different power is often unambiguous and correct. Occasionally however, this automatic assignment is wrong. Moreover, the automatic identification of a power with an inappropriate behaviour is based on a very simple trigger mechanism (e.g. evocation of an unpleasant feeling → UDINOR). The understanding of guilt provided by UDINOR is thus of very simple

nature. It can be true on a very narrow sense but may not reflect the big picture. The automatically induced understanding of guilt in a UDINOR situation does not take into account overall, situational, legal, social, logical, and other factors.

The quick automatic activation of UDINOR after an own unpleasant feeling (i.e. the quick automatic assignment of an external culprit) and the negative contents of automatic thoughts (which for example blame the character or the behaviour of the interlocutor for his delay – and not possible unfavourable circumstances) lead to a rash judgement even if the circumstances are actually different. This phenomenon to prefer dispositional instead of situational explanations can be proven in experiments and is known as *fundamental attribution error*. It means that humans (erroneously) tend to hold individuals rather than situations responsible for adverse developments [Ross, 1977]. When UDINOR is generated then almost no situational arguments appear automatically but nearly exclusively dispositional attributions instead.

There is a strong coupling between the cognitive UE impulses NESPECT and UDINOR. If NESPECT is evoked in the perceiving individual (e.g. due to an insult) then an automatic generation of UDINOR often follows immediately which is directed against the originator of the evocation of NESPECT (e.g. against the originator of the insult). This intra-individual NESPECT → UDINOR cascade works automatically. The following kind of reaction to the typical, UDINOR accompanying urge for a pejorative rebuke for the other power depends inter alia on the impulse control of the individual.

A pejorative rebuke (following on UDINOR) would immediately evoke NESPECT in the other individual. This is the underlying intention of a rebuke: the painful NESPECT impulse generated by the rebuke shall motivate the other individual to change its behaviour in the future. This inter-individual UDINOR → NESPECT cascade is also important in bringing up children. However, the two cascades mentioned hold the danger of a mutual building up: two individuals can mutually evoke NESPECT in each other, what immediately and automatically results in the generation of UDINOR (and an urge for another pejorative rebuke) in the respective individuals. Thus UDINOR serves to regulate the relationships to other individuals but also comprises (when used extensively) the risk to destroy exactly those relationships. Note that the behaviour of an individual in a UDINOR situation has nothing to do with instrumentally deployed behaviour such as voluntary insults, malicious gossip fuelled by positive emotions (GE), malevolence, purposive vileness, or mobbing [Berkowitz, 1993]. UDINOR exclusively denotes an automatically developing unpleasant emotion (UE). As a consequence of this automatically generated UE and under the influence of the latter, the described behavioural forms emerge.

4.2.7 IDINOR

Definition: *IDINOR* [aidamər] (abbreviation of “I did something not right”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of an own inappropriate behaviour.

Of course the own behaviour can have adverse effects on an individual too. If such an inappropriate own behaviour is discovered then the IDINOR detector activates a warning signal in the form of the UE (IDINOR) automatically.

IDINOR is similar to the cognitive UE impulse UDINOR but refers to the behaviour of the perceiving individual itself. The latter perceives an own behaviour, i.e. an action or an omission, which is classified as inappropriate automatically. An inappropriate behaviour is –

like in a UDINOR situation – from the perspective of the perceiving individual an (intentional or unintentional) own behaviour which evokes an unwanted unpleasant feeling in the perceiving individual (for example a UE or a pain) or which violates its own opinions. Thus the generation of IDINOR often follows a different cognitive UE impulse (for example ITNOUT or SOTINA). A classic example from the realm of IDINOR is the uncertainty whether one has locked the own front door safely.

Viewed objectively, there are surprisingly many causes for a wrong own behaviour: erroneous own assessments (for example of a situation or a person), ignorance, lack of time, carelessness or thoughtlessness, credulity, an existing ambush, difficult anticipation of the consequences, not considered consequences, too late arising helpful ideas, or too late appearing important information. Given the number and the importance of those critical decision making factors, a flawless human behaviour – as occasionally glorified in cinema films – might be more the exception than the rule in reality. Nevertheless, whether the IDINOR detector classifies an own behaviour as inappropriate and generates an IDINOR impulse automatically does not depend on such factors but solely on the mentioned criteria for the classification of a behaviour as inappropriate (i.e. on a preceding generation of an unwanted unpleasant feeling or on a preceding violation of own opinions).

As described in the definition of IDINOR, an automatic generation of this cognitive UE impulse requires that the individual perceives (or recognizes) an own inappropriate behaviour (which lead to an unfavourable situation). Only such a perception enables the generation of IDINOR in the perceiving individual. If this perception lacks then a generation of IDINOR is not possible.

The IDINOR called UE is per se unpleasant. This automatically generated UE can appear with a very high intensity. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of this automatically generated UE are guilt, regret, frustration, stress, despair, or grief.

In an IDINOR situation (i.e. a situation in which IDINOR dominates) automatic thoughts (i.e. automatically generated thoughts) appear typically. They focus on the cause of the UE generation, on an own mistake, i.e. on an own inappropriate behaviour that has been perceived. The contents of those automatic thoughts are of descriptive nature (“I completely screwed up my presentation.”), of explaining nature (“My presentation was too long and not fluently enough.”), showing possible consequences (“I probably couldn’t convince the audience.”), at odds with the situation (“Why couldn’t that work out better for me?”), of blaming others character (“The audience was noisy and unfriendly.”), of self-accusing character (“I should have prepared better for the presentation.”), of correcting nature (“Next time I will prepare more.”), of catastrophizing character (“My bad performance could get about.”), or – rarely – of de-escalating character (“My next presentation will be better.”). Most of those automatic thoughts fuel the existing UE. With automatically appearing pictures or language they keep the UE generating situation vividly alive in the consciousness of the perceiving individual. For example, they focus (again and again) on the cause of the UE generation or on its possible consequences.

In case of a succeeding UE phase (i.e. the UE persists over a longer period) dominated by IDINOR the activity of automatic thoughts can lead to circle of thought (i.e. many automatic thoughts focus on one specific topic and maintain an approximately constant intensity of the current UE), to scene building of thought (i.e. automatic thoughts form a vivid imagination leading to an increase of the intensity of the current UE), and even to insomnia (i.e. to problems to fall asleep or to sleep through). Sometimes a lack of drive appears.

In and after an IDINOR situation, an individual has different behavioural options – dependent

on its abilities (e.g. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options). These include to correct its behaviour (for example to make something better, to make it up, to excuse oneself), to treat oneself in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (e.g. self-castigation, elimination)), to communicate with other individuals, to seek help, to ignore the IDINOR impulse, to find a reason why the own inappropriate behaviour was a correct behaviour (justification), to accept ones inappropriate behaviour, to wait until the impulse loses its sharpness, or to change one's future behaviour in order to prevent similar IDINOR experiences. A seldom reaction to an own inappropriate behaviour which is perceived by the individual as being severe is to commit suicide. The impression of hopelessness, i.e. the perceived lack of a way out, is a key factor in the decision of an individual to commit suicide [Beck, 1975; Dyer, 1984; Salter, 1990].

If an individual has shown an inappropriate behaviour which lead to IDINOR then there is an increased probability for subsequent errors and for further IDINOR generations.

An important aspect of IDINOR is that IDINOR does not – contrary to other cognitive UE impulses – work as an advance warning but merely appears after a past own inappropriate behaviour.

Similar to the loss aversion, the activation of IDINOR can trigger a change in behaviour of the individual in order to prevent future painful IDINOR experiences. For example, continuing strong gains at the stock market can lead to IDINOR in an individual and to a regret for not having earlier invested in shares. This can trigger an investment in shares in order to participate in the current bull market too. The individual thus shows a guilt or *regret aversion* [Zeelenberg, 1996] and strives to improve its behaviour. Note that this is not a rational, gain maximizing but an emotional decision making.

Having made a mistake or the mere activation of IDINOR can quickly be exploited by other individuals if they become aware of the (supposed) mistake. Ekman postulates that the emotion guilt does not have an own facial expression therefore [Ekman, 2003].

4.2.8 DISLIKIT

Definition: *DISLIKIT* [dislaikit] (abbreviation of “I dislike it/this”) denotes the UE which develops automatically from the perception of a strong similarity to a negatively valued component of the individual value system.

The DISLIKIT detector identifies objects which can have adverse effects on the individual. If such an object is recognized then a signal in the form of the UE (DISLIKIT) is activated automatically. The DISLIKIT detector supports the individual in the quick assessment of the continuing stream of impressions to which it is exposed and in the differentiation of the unwanted from the wanted ones.

DISLIKIT is one of the most frequently occurring cognitive UE impulses. This cognitive UE impulse is based on the individual value system of the perceiving individual. The individual value system denotes the (virtual) totality of all current values and assessments of an individual of its world, plus the corresponding assessment mechanisms. Beside those mechanisms it includes many separate components to each of which a specific variable value (or valence) is assigned. Each (real or abstract) object that can be valued can form the basis of such a component. Such an object has a material or immaterial consistence. It is part of the inanimate world or of the living world (of the same species or of a different species).

Examples for such an object are a food, a sound, a piece of music, a colour, a smell, a different individual, a species, a certain place, an event, a specific fashion accessory, a literary work, a newspaper, a process, an activity, a kind of sport, a school subject, an opinion, or an abstract concept. Comparable to the position of a slide control, a positive or a negative value is then assigned to each of those components. A negative value means that the individual is refusing this component (or the underlying object, respectively). A positive value on the other hand corresponds to a liking or a preference of the individual for this component and means that the individual likes this component (e.g. that it approves a certain view).

Note that despite its simple structure, this individual value system allows very sophisticated individual assessments or judgements of things. For example, an individual of integrity can assign a negative value to the component “steal” and consistently to this a positive value to the component “not steal”. A different individual however can assign a positive value to the component “not steal” but also a positive one to the component “steal” (for example in the sense of Robin Hood). In general, the values of the individual value system reflect to a great extent the character and the personality of an individual.

Most values of the individual value system change with time. Some values change frequently (for example, appetite and repletion, i.e. the preference for and the dislike of food, alternate several times each day in people from industrialized countries), others change in longer intervals (e.g. the lust for sex), again others do virtually not change during a lifetime (e.g. the sexual attitude).

The assignment of a value to a component is carried out through one or several automatic mechanisms. Some values are dependent on the age of the individual, they are subject to mechanisms of the *age-related assessment*. Via those mechanisms specific preferences or dislikes develop in individuals of a species at a certain age. For example, children all over the world are enthusiastic about playthings. With the entry into the adult life however, this enthusiasm decreases substantially. The same phenomenon is visible in many other (mammalian) species: young animals play, adult animals do not. Another example is the interest in sex in adult age.

Other values of the individual value system are affected by changes of the body state. The change of those values is induced by the *body state-related assessment*. Examples are the refusal of food in case of repletion, the liking of water in case of thirst, the preference for cooling things (e.g. an ice cream) in very hot weather, or the preference for warming things (e.g. a fondue) in very cold weather.

Again other values of the individual value system are innate and base on *to innate values-related assessments*. Examples for innate values are the strict preference for sweet food of new-born babies, the unquestioning love of mothers for their offspring, or the sudden interest of girls in a romantic relationship with boys and vice versa in adolescence. Furthermore, girls and women are world-wide filled with enthusiasm for babies and children.

Of great importance is the automatic mechanism of the *feeling-related assessment*. If an unpleasant feeling, for example a pain or a cognitive UE impulse, is generated in an individual then an object of relation (e.g. the originator) to this unpleasant feeling, i.e. an object which the perceiving individual can relate to the generation of this feeling (e.g. causal, temporal), is negatively assessed automatically. For example, if the perceiving individual experiences a disrespect for the own personality and an unpleasant NESPECT impulse is thus induced then the originator of this disrespect (typically a different individual) is assigned automatically, i.e. without any voluntary activity of the perceiving individual [Garcia, 1990], a negative (precisely: a more negative) value in the value system of the perceiving individual

(so to speak the slide control is adjusted towards a more negative value). On the other hand, if a pleasant feeling, for example a GE impulse, is generated in an individual then an object of relation (e.g. the originator) to this pleasant feeling, i.e. an object which the perceiving individual can relate to the generation of this feeling (e.g. causal, temporal), is positively assessed automatically. For example, if a soccer player kicks into the net and if this goal causes the generation of a pleasant cognitive GE impulse (ITWOUT³) in a fan of this soccer team, then the scorer is assigned automatically, i.e. without any voluntary activity of the perceiving individual, a positive (precisely: a more positive) value in the individual value system of this particular fan (so to speak the slide control is adjusted towards a more positive value). The same happens if the perceiving individual stays at a dangerous place where it feels threatened (i.e. where it perceives the generation of SOTINA): then a (more) negative value is assigned to this place by the feeling-related assessment mechanism automatically. A classic example is an inedible food which the individual has to vomit: similarly, this food is assigned a negative value (which often lasts for long) in the value system of the perceiving individual automatically. On the other hand, if the ingestion of a food evokes pleasant feelings then this food (precisely: its component in the value system) is assigned a positive value automatically. If the individual perceives an object later which strongly resembles to or equals a negatively valued component of its value system then the cognitive UE impulse DISLIKIT is generated automatically. On the other hand, if the individual perceives an object which strongly resembles to or equals a positively valued component of its value system then LIKIT⁴ is activated automatically. In this manner, the individual value system first assesses (new) sensory impressions automatically and saves the result of this assessment in the form of a value. Those values enable the individual later a rapid assessment of new impressions and situations thanks to its experiences from the past: in case of a strong similarity of the currently perceived object with a past one, a signal corresponding to the value (or valence) for the object of the past is generated immediately (e.g. DISLIKIT). This information is available to the individual immediately in order to serve as a guideline for an appropriate behaviour. Examples for negatively valued objects which activate DISLIKIT are a nasty smell, an unappetizing food, pests, an inedible berry, vomit, a screeching noise, an ugly picture, an unkempt vagabond, a filthy place, a dangerous animal, a poisonous plant, a yawning chasm, or a filthy habit of a different individual. After this manner, the individual value system enables a rapid emotional assessment of new situations through automatic emotional learning. The DISLIKIT called UE is per se unpleasant. However, this UE appears in most cases with a comparatively (i.e. compared to the other cognitive UE impulses) low intensity. The expressions (or the overall emotional manifestations) of this automatically generated UE range typically from dislike, disapproval, aversion, timidity, repulsion, disgust, antipathy, distaste, hatred, and contempt to horror. Disgust⁵ occurs worldwide [Ekman, 2003]. Already Darwin described that the expressions disgust and contempt can hardly be distinguished and are thus closely related with one another [Darwin, 1872]. It is typical for DISLIKIT that this cognitive UE impulse comes along with a strong urge to distance oneself from the perceived object (e.g. by turning away, by zapping to a different channel, by refusal, by avoidance). This urge to turn away from a negatively valued object can even be seen in the involuntary movement of the human pupil: if a person looks at an

³ ITWOUT (“It works out (like I want it to)”) is a cognitive GE impulse and the counterpart of ITNOUT.

⁴ LIKIT (abbreviation of “I like it/this”) is a cognitive GE impulse and the counterpart of DISLIKIT.

⁵ The facial expression of disgust tends to discourage entry into the body or to encourage discharge [Rozin, 2008].

object that he or she does not like then the pupil involuntarily shrinks (such as if the eye would like to let through as few optical information as possible from the unpleasant object). On the other hand, if the person spots an object that he or she likes then the pupils increase automatically [Morris, 1985].

In a DISLIKIT situation (i.e. a situation in which DISLIKIT prevails) automatic thoughts can appear in addition to the emotion (i.e. DISLIKIT) and the automatically arising behavioural reaction (i.e. the urge to distance oneself). Those automatic thoughts refer to the cause of the UE generation, i.e. to the negatively valued object that has been perceived. They are of descriptive nature (“I don’t like this colleague.”), of explaining nature (“He always speaks so long.”), showing possible consequences (“He keeps me from working on other tasks.”), at odds with the situation (“Why can’t he be brief?”), of blaming others nature (“He only tells nonsense.”), of self-accusing nature (“I shouldn’t have attended this meeting.”), of catastrophizing character (“Like this the meeting is going to last forever.”), or – rarely – of de-escalating nature (“Perhaps things will work out better today.”).

Typical kinds of behaviour of an individual in and after a DISLIKIT situation are – dependent on its abilities (i.e. knowledge, skills, impulse control) and the specific situation (which limits the number of available options) – to get rid of the object, to have a spit, to turn away, to avoid the object, to approach the object in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination)), to communicate with other individuals about the object, to warn other individuals, to seek help, to ignore the impulse, or to wait until or if the object disappears by itself. Furthermore, the individual can change its behaviour in order to prevent similar DISLIKIT generations in the future.

Concerning the human non-verbal behaviour, many gestures of dislike are similar to each other world-wide [Darwin, 1872]. Among those are the spitting, the turning-up one’s nose, the holding one’s nose, the putting one’s hand over one’s ears (against undesired acoustic signals), the touch of the lips with the extended forefinger (ditto), the shaking of the head (the head is moved from one side to the other in which the turning to the left is equally strong as the turning to the right), the lowering of the palm(s) (the palm is turned to the bottom and repeatedly lowered rhythmically), and the crossing one’s hands (the palms are turned to the front and moved several times to the left and to the right and cross each other). All those gestures are spread widely or world-wide [Morris, 1994].

The processes of the feeling-related assessment (i.e. the automatic change of values in the individual value system after the appearance of a feeling, for example a cognitive impulse) correspond to an automatic emotional learning. Such an emotional learning is the basis of the *conditioning*. Conditioning means that an event is paired with a second one which predicts the first one, e.g. if a bell rings then food is available. Among other things it has been shown that an object needs to be in such a relation to the appearing feeling that this relation can be recognized from the perceiving individual in order to enable a succeeding automatic reaction to the object [Hearst, 1988]. In advertising conditioning is used in order to pair a brand with pleasant emotions.

Some objects activate more or less disgust in humans. Disgust has to be learned first in infancy [Rozin, 2008]. Objects which often evoke disgust are secretions of the body of other individuals such as vomit, mucus, pus, faeces, urine, blood, spittle, and sweat; fallen off parts of the human body of other individuals such as hairs, dandruff, nails, or eyelashes; vermin such as worms, maggots, woodlice, or spiders; and spoiled food. Virtually all of these objects can be potentially contaminated by germs. Individuals perceive the potential existence of those pathogens (e.g. by the smell, by vision, by learning). The resulting generation of

DISLIKIT aims at protecting the individual against potentially dangerous germs. Note that the simplicity of the slide control function of the feeling-related assessment also involves disadvantages (and even dangers) for the perceiving individual. An important disadvantage is that the slide control function corresponds only to a very rudimentary emotional longer-term memory. With only a few (or even only one) bad – since in the perceiving individual UE generating – actions, a different individual can destroy countless earlier positive assessments in the value system of the perceiving individual. A long lasting relationship for example can in such a way automatically be devaluated from a top positive to a negative value in the value system of the perceiving individual – although such a strong devaluation perhaps does not reflect the overall real situation. On the other hand, an individual that usually behaves in a despicable way can purposeful with a few nice actions automatically cause positive assessments and a positive value in the value system of the perceiving individual which overall does not reflect reality (and which makes the perceiving individual vulnerable for further despicableness). Both cases are potentially disadvantageous or even dangerous for the perceiving individual since important experiences of the past remain widely unconsidered in those assessments. An advantage of the simplicity of this system is however that negative values in the individual value system can gradually be changed if the perceiving individual strives for this goal. Through a gradual approach to a negatively valued object and with corresponding positive experiences an increasingly more positive value of the underlying component results. In this manner, a dislike of a particular food can be reduced or even be changed into a predilection. For example, many small children don't like strongly smelling cheese – what often changes with repeated expositions over the years. This technique was already well-known in antiquity and serves as a basis for the confrontation therapy [Michael, 2009].

DISLIKIT appears with a – compared to all other cognitive UE impulses – low intensity. Why is this the case? A UE with a smaller intensity causes less stress to the perceiving individual. The real purpose of the activation of DISLIKIT is to distance the individual from aversive stimuli. This is the reason that a strong urge to distance oneself accompanies the DISLIKIT impulse. With the realization of this urge (for example by turning away, avoidance) the purpose of the generation of DISLIKIT is already fulfilled. A stronger UE is thus unnecessary. The attention of the individual is instantly available for new impressions. Most DISLIKIT evoking objects represent no acute danger. And in case of danger the specialized cognitive UE impulses (e.g. SOTINA, NESPECT) go into action immediately. A higher intensity of DISLIKIT would be inefficient, counter-productive, and unnecessary.

The human individual value system includes also innate and age-related values. The majority of values however is affected by the body state-related assessment and especially by the feeling-related assessment, i.e. by assessments with reference to the specific prevailing environment of the perceiving individual. The two mechanisms adjust most values of the individual value system in a variable fashion adapted to the specific external and internal requirements of the individual. These processes take place automatically without an active assistance of the individual.

5. Developments during infancy

In infancy the different cognitive UE impulses appear at different points in time for the first time. The UE appears in the baby from birth on. There are several indications of this. First, the new-born feels hunger in regular intervals – an obviously unpleasant experience which causes the baby to cry every single time. Also DISLIKIT and LIKIT appear directly after birth for the first time. New-borns strictly prefer sweet food. They show their refusal of other tastes (e.g. sour, bitter, salty) or their intention to stop ingestion clearly by turning their head aside or by moving it to the nape of the neck. Furthermore, 4-month-old infants prefer consonant music to dissonant versions [Zentner, 1996].

ITNOUT probably appears from birth on too. Already new-born humans 2-48 hours of age react with crying if they first receive a sucrose solution each time after a gentle forehead stroking and then the sweet solution suddenly fails to materialize after this forehead stroking. Unconditioned new-borns (which got the sucrose solution without a preceding forehead stroking) don't show this behaviour [Blass, 1984]. At the age of 2 weeks babies react with crying if the breast is taken away during drinking. At the age of 2-3 months the infant cries if a favourite toy animal disappears [Wolff, 1969]. The baby shows clear signs of dissatisfaction if its doing is disturbed by something [Ekman, 2003]. ITNOUT appears in the first months of life also in that respect that the baby defends itself against a hindrance of its movements. UDINOR appears around the fourth month of the infant's life. At this age the emotional expressions of the infant are directed toward the culprit. Beating, biting, and kicking of infants can be observed very early [Ekman, 2003].

From an age of about five months up SOTINA becomes obvious. Infants develop in appropriate situations (e.g. in case of farewell, separation) a strong separation anxiety (i.e. the fear for losing its mother, father, or another person to whom the small child relates very closely). The separation anxiety is strongest in the first years of life and causes the infant not to go away too far from its (protecting) parents – what increases its chance of survival on average. The separation anxiety decreases in the following years but still lasts many years in infancy [Largo, 2007]. One or two months after the appearance of the separation anxiety another form of SOTINA follows. It manifests itself distinctively by a child's fear of strangers. Dependent on the intensity of SOTINA the infant shows different non-verbal or verbal forms of distancing such as a diffident smile, an averting gaze, a safety-seeking gaze to a person to whom it relates very closely, a timorous gazing to the stranger, a seeking protection at a person to whom it relates very closely, a hiding, a weeping, or a crying [Bowlby, 1973].

The cognitive UE impulse NESPECT can be observed after the first year of life at the latest. HASAD appears in infants about 1½ years of age. They show an envy behaviour concerning resources of other individuals such as toys, various things of value, and the attention of the mother. Already before that age they grab things that seem exciting to them but they are not aware that those things are owned by other children [Frankel, 1977]. Instead, they still view the world as a kind of land of milk and honey where one can grab whatever one likes. IDINOR and IDIR can be observed from an age of 2 years up. The evocation of these cognitive UE impulses requires larger cognitive abilities: the individual needs a concept from its own self and the ability to automatically connect an own past behaviour (an action or an omission) with an unfavourable consequence in the present (or past or future). In general, a cognitive impulse can be generated in the infant only if the cognitive processes required for its generation are available.

The evocation of many cognitive impulses becomes more sophisticated during the years of life. For example, an infant first has to learn the various subtle verbal and non-verbal forms of disrespect before the latter can activate with NESPECT and DISLIKIT a certain protection for the individual. Similarly, small children behave completely innocent towards many dangers (e.g. towards wild animals in the zoo, towards stretches of water) because they are not yet able to recognize them and thus no generation of DISLIKIT or SOTINA can take place. Also the disgust of harmful, potentially contaminated substances (e.g. faeces) is not present in 2-year-olds but has to be understood and learned first [Rozin, 2008].

Simple UE impulses shape the emotional development of a child too. In its first months of life a baby does not show any dislike of heights. This is changing with the beginning of the crawling stage of the baby (at around 7 months of life). With the crawling a wariness of heights develops [Campos, 1992]. Crawling also leads to (unintentional) falling. If this occurs the simple UE trigger falling activates an unpleasant UE in the infant. This UE causes the infant through automatic emotional learning to shy away from heights in future.

6. Evolutionary aspects

Emotions are of fundamental importance for the survival of individuals and their genes. They drive significantly the approach of individuals to other objects and the removal of them. For example this is the case in dangerous situations (fight versus flight), during the search for food (ingestion versus turning away), or during the sexual behaviour (attraction versus lack of interest). Emotions developed with the living creatures over a very long period of time during evolution. Panksepp showed that the underlying neuronal systems of emotions in humans and animals (of kin species) strongly resemble one another [Panksepp, 1998]. If cognitive UE impulses (such as ITNOUT, SOTINA, NESPECT, ...) developed as basic building blocks of negative emotions in nature over millions of years then, inevitably, they have to be explainable by evolutionary aspects. Is that the case?

Evolutionary explainable means that individuals which originally possessed a certain characteristic (e.g. a cognitive detector with SOTINA generation) must have gained advantages through this characteristic on average to pass on their genes compared to those individuals that did not possess such a characteristic. In the course of long-time periods such characteristics succeed within the gene pool of a species (for example through natural selection). In the end, all individuals of the species possess the advantageous characteristic and the characteristic becomes a part of the individuals of this species.

SOTINA: An individual with a detector with SOTINA generation is automatically warned by a signal from this detector (by an unpleasant inner uneasiness (SOTINA)) if the individual recognizes a cue that something from its resources is or could be taken away. This signal urges the individual for example to a flight or fight reaction. A loss of resources is potentially disadvantageous for the fitness of an individual. The fitness of an individual denotes its ability to pass on its genes to descendants which generate offspring. A timely warning of an imminent loss of resources can help to prevent the latter since the individual can take appropriate defence measures (such as flight, hiding, seeking help). In case of a lurking predator, the advantage of a SOTINA warning system becomes especially obvious: the latter directly increases the chance of survival of the individual compared to those individuals that

do not have such a warning system and thus do not get any warning signals of the dangerous enemy. Higher chances of survival of individuals with detectors with SOTINA generation prolong their average lifetime. A longer lifetime increases the opportunities for reproduction. More opportunities for reproduction lead to more descendants on average. Thus, individuals with detectors with SOTINA generation have a higher fitness compared to individuals without detectors with SOTINA generation. After this manner, the characteristic “detector with SOTINA generation” could spread more and more in the gene pool of the species until finally all individuals of the species had it at their disposal.

ITNOUT: An individual with a detector with ITNOUT generation is bothered by an unpleasant inner uneasiness (ITNOUT) if it perceives an obstacle. This unpleasant emotion drives or motivates the individual to make efforts to eliminate the obstacle which became virtually physically unpleasant – and to eliminate with the obstacle the unpleasant UE. The successful removal of the obstacle however increases the probability that the individual still reaches its goal. Individuals without detectors with ITNOUT generation lack this additional unpleasant drive. Therefore they take less consistent action against a hindrance and thus on average have a lower probability to reach their goal. Individuals with detectors with ITNOUT generation have a deciding advantage with those detectors because in nature the striving of an individual often serves its survival or that one of its genes (e.g. to search for food, to search for a safe shelter (also for the offspring), reproduction). Higher rates in reaching the goals in those areas increase the fitness of the individual. In this way, the characteristic “detector with ITNOUT generation” could spread more and more in the course of the time until all individuals of the species had this characteristic finally.

NESPECT: The NESPECT impulse warns individuals of (currently) hostile other individuals. By means of appropriate countermeasures (e.g. to distance oneself from or to cooperate with such individuals) physical injuries or worse can be prevented. Moreover, the unpleasant NESPECT signal causes the individual to act more carefully in many social situations (e.g. in social hierarchies, in groups, in territoriality) what decreases the probability of unnecessary clashes and thus of physical injuries or worse for individuals with detectors with NESPECT generation. In contrast, an unreasonable individual without detector with NESPECT generation can only be stopped by physical force. This however increases the probability that this individual is (seriously) wounded in a clash. Individuals with detectors with NESPECT generation have a longer lifespan on average and thus more opportunities for reproduction and a higher fitness than individuals without detectors with NESPECT generation. Therefore this characteristic spread more and more in the gene pool of the species in the course of time until every individual of the species had this characteristic finally.

HASAD: Individuals with detectors with HASAD generation feel automatically an unpleasant UE (HASAD) if they perceive an appropriate advantage of a different individual. To get rid of it they will try to eliminate the inequality perceived by them, for example through protest, through theft of the resource, or through efforts to gain an own similar advantage. Through such behaviours they often attain an increase of their own resources. This is especially true compared to individuals without detectors with HASAD generation since those individuals are neither automatically nor emotionally (i.e. unpleasantly) bothered about the supposed inequality (because of the missing HASAD impulse). To have more resources increases the chances of survival in tendency. This enables more opportunities for reproduction (also as a consequence of a higher attractiveness because of more resources) and a higher fitness. Therefore the characteristic spread more and more over a long period of time until all individuals of the species had that characteristic finally.

NOWEL: *NOWEL* vanishes not only after a plausible all-clear but also after the perception of a real reduction of the own physical integrity. This cognitive UE impulse thus serves especially an early care of the own health. The generation of the unpleasant *NOWEL* impulse forces the individual to deal with the cause of the *NOWEL* generation. An individual with detector with *NOWEL* generation therefore looks inevitably earlier or longer after the cause of the UE generation (e.g. an injury) what increases its chances of survival on average compared to individuals without detectors with *NOWEL* generation. This enhances its opportunities for reproduction and its fitness. Over a long period of time this characteristic therefore spread more and more in the gene pool of the species until all individuals of the species had that characteristic at their disposal.

UDINOR: The *UDINOR* generation often occurs in an individual as a consequence of a different UE impulse (e.g. after *ITNOUT*, after *SOTINA*, after *NESPECT*, after *HASAD*) because of a corresponding (adverse) behaviour of a different individual. Such a preceding generation of a different UE impulse is an indication of a potential disadvantage for the perceiving individual. The following generation of *UDINOR* leads often directly to a rebuke (e.g. non-verbally, physically) for the other individual what in turn generates an unpleasant *NESPECT* impulse in this individual. To prevent the unpleasant experience in the future the other individual has an increased motivation to change its behaviour. Such a change in behaviour is achieved less often by an individual without detector with *UDINOR* generation since there is no additional *UDINOR* impulse driving it to the exertion of a rebuke for the other individual. The mentioned change in behaviour however changes the odds in favour of the perceiving individual (e.g. concerning various interests, leadership, mating, ingestion, defence). It directly improves important circumstances of the perceiving individual and its fitness on average (compared to individuals without detectors with *UDINOR* generation). The characteristic “detector with *UDINOR* generation” thus won through in the gene pool of the species finally. Of great importance is *UDINOR* in the upbringing since the offspring learn through the unpleasant inter-individual *UDINOR* → *NESPECT* cascade not to carry out adverse (e.g. dangerous) behaviour. This effect contributes to the increase of the fitness of an individual with detector with *UDINOR* generation compared to an individual without detector with *UDINOR* generation.

IDINOR: The unpleasant *IDINOR* impulse refers to an own adverse (e.g. dangerous) behaviour. In order to prevent the unpleasant *IDINOR* in the future the individual is motivated to correct its past adverse behaviour or to change it in the future. The correction or abandonment of adverse behaviours is on average more likely for individuals with detectors with *IDINOR* generation since individuals without detectors with *IDINOR* generation have less incentive or information to do so (since they lack the automatic and unpleasant *IDINOR* signal). Therefore, the fitness of individuals with detectors with *IDINOR* generation improved and also the spreading of this characteristic in the gene pool of the species – until every individual of the species finally had this characteristic.

DISLIKIT: Correct assessments which fruits or plants are uneatable, which other individuals are hostile, or which places are dangerous increase the lifespan of an individual with detector with *DISLIKIT* generation on average (compared to individuals without detectors with *DISLIKIT* generation). A longer lifespan provides the individual more opportunities for reproduction what typically increases the number of descendants. Individuals with detectors with *DISLIKIT* generation thus have a higher fitness than individuals without detectors with *DISLIKIT* generation. Therefore, the characteristic “detector with *DISLIKIT* generation” spread more and more in the gene pool of the species in the course of time until all individuals

of the species finally had this characteristic.

In summary it can be stated that the cognitive UE impulses can be explained conclusively from an evolutionary point of view. Cognitive UE impulses provide on average higher chances of survival to their owners. However, not only a lack but in the individual case also a hyperactivity of cognitive UE impulses can have a negative effect on the individual.

Nevertheless, because of the processes described above such disadvantageous characteristics can't be successful in the gene pool of a species in the long run.

7. Discussion

Besides the indicative and to the present related form (e.g. for ITNOUT: “It does not work out (like I want it to)”) all cognitive UE impulses have also automatically appearing subjunctive forms (e.g. subjunctive to the present related ITNOUT: “It could not work out (like I want it to)”). Furthermore, many cognitive UE impulses have also to the past related forms (e.g. indicative to the past related ITNOUT: “It did not work out (like I want it to)”) or to the future related forms (e.g. indicative to the future related ITNOUT: “It will not work out (like I want it to)”). Also for the forms which are related to the past or to the future, the assessment always takes place in the present (“... (like I want it to)”). The automatic assessment about the past or the future always takes place at the current moment (for example that a hindrance of an own important striving in fact has taken place or that it will take place).

Note that the different cognitive UE impulses can appear shortly after each other in different combinations. All negative emotions (such as jealousy, disappointment, despair) are shaped by signals from one or several of those eight building blocks.

Such as negative emotions are based on eight cognitive UE impulses, positive emotions build on eight cognitive GE impulses (ITWOUT, NOTINA, RESPECT, HAVAD, DOWEL, UDIR, IDIR, and LIKIT⁶). These eight building blocks form the basis of positive emotions [Tscharmi, 2019b].

The UE which appears after the activation of a cognitive UE impulse holds the individual in an unpleasant state. In addition it often suggests the necessity for a quick action. It urges the individual more to a quick than to a carefully thought out behaviour – such as in the wilderness a quick flight increases the chance of survival often more than a considerable thought. The UE disappears rapidly if the underlying problem of its activation does not exist anymore.

The activation of a cognitive UE impulse is often followed by automatic thoughts (in the form of pictures or language). Interestingly, many of these thoughts focus on aspects which are identical for all cognitive UE impulses. Among them are descriptive, explaining, showing possible consequences, at odds with the situation [Janoff-Bulman, 1988], blaming others, self-accusing, and catastrophizing automatic thoughts. This indicates that those automatic thoughts are fed by discrete, independent neuronal functional units which are activated after the generation of the UE. Constantly appearing automatic thoughts keep the underlying problem persistently in the consciousness of the individual. In addition to the unpleasant UE they make

⁶ The eight abbreviations denote: ITWOUT: “It works out (like I want it to)”, NOTINA: “Nobody takes something away from me”, RESPECT: “I am respected”, HAVAD: “I have an advantage”, DOWEL: “I do feel well”, UDIR: “You did something right”, IDIR: “I did something right”, LIKIT: “I like it/this”.

it difficult for the individual to deal with other tasks. The individual is forced to deal with the problem and to find a solution. Regards content a certain enrichment of information through automatic thoughts takes place but many automatic thoughts are of negative or even destructive nature with little relation to reality. They focus primarily on negative aspects of the actual problem. This is consistent with the findings of Beck who describes automatic thoughts as negative regards content [Beck, 1976]. This is also reflected in the common categories of automatic thoughts for the cognitive UE impulses: most of them are negatively coloured. The unpleasant UE and the bothering automatic thoughts urge the individual to an appropriate behaviour.

Many behavioural options are identical for all cognitive UE impulses. Their overall number is limited. Most behavioural options serve the aim to terminate the current unpleasant UE. Other forms of behaviour are chosen to prevent similar situations in the future. Decisions for a certain behaviour are often made quickly and impulsively.

There are dispositional differences in the generation of cognitive UE impulses, i.e. differences which are due to different personalities of different individuals. One reason for those differences are different individual value systems. Some persons experience more envy (or HASAD generations) than others. If for example an individual attaches no importance to the resource “power” then this individual is less likely to experience HASAD when perceiving an individual with power compared to another individual which strives for precisely this resource. Analogously, a person who has lost an object which was unimportant to him or her will quicker recover from this loss than an individual for which this object was highly significant. Furthermore, individuals who did not learn disgust of a certain object do not experience DISLIKIT if they perceive this object [Rozin, 2008].

The generation of simple UE impulses bases directly on the signals of specialized physical receptors (sensors) of the body. A healthy individual can depend on this *deterministic* system of the UE generation in its daily life. For example, if its instantly available energy reserves fall below a certain level then the UE is activated by hunger. If its body moves through its weight from a certain height downwards then the UE is activated by the falling.

The same UE is activated in a completely different way by the cognitive UE impulses of the human emotion system. Its generation bases here on logical detectors which indirectly derive the desired parameters (e.g. a hindrance, a taking away, a disrespect) from already otherwise existing information (e.g. visual, acoustic information). Such a derivation is often linked with uncertainty (especially for subjunctive cognitive UE impulses). Thus this generation of the UE is of *stochastic* nature (i.e. dependent on probabilities) and the laws of the detection theory apply. The mechanisms that activate the cognitive UE impulses are part of an individual biological alarm system. This system developed during evolution such that it serves the survival of the individual and its genes on average. It is specialized on the discovery of dangerous situations – even if there are only smallest signs of a danger. Therefore smallest plausible appearing cues of possible threats are systematically intensified by automatic thoughts (via pictures, language) and through catastrophizing multiplied. The automatically generated UE alarms the individual and suggests in addition a necessity for a quick action. Through those measures the miss probability, i.e. the probability that the individual by mistake misses a real severe threat, shall be minimized.

This biological alarm system has some serious drawbacks. First, according to the detection theory the decrease of the miss probability in a given system leads to an increase of the false alarm probability (and vice versa). Thus this biological alarm system generates many false alarms. Such false alarms are not only disturbing but they can cause negative effects

themselves. This is for example the case if the defence measures of the individual cause damage to the individual (e.g. through an unintentional own injury, an unnecessary medical treatment, suicide). Moreover, the biological alarm system was optimized during evolution with respect to the totality of all individuals of a species and concerning the relevant threats in the past. However, in an individual case or concerning novel threats the activity of the cognitive impulses – amplification, impetus – can have a negative effect on or even be deadly for the individual.

In the human brain several areas are involved in negative emotions. The amygdala is among other things activated in case of fear. It is also involved in the automatic detection of threat [Öhman, 2005]. The insula is important for the perception of feelings of all kind (e.g. disgust) [Craig, 2008]. This is also true for the cingulate cortex. The hypothalamus plays an essential role in goal-oriented behaviours. Moreover, it provides neuronal circuits that are physically separated from each other for threats through predators (SOTINA) and for threats through dominant conspecifics (NESPECT) [Motta, 2009]. This is a strong indication that there might be physically separated neuronal circuits in the brain for the different cognitive UE impulses.

8. Conclusions

This paper postulates that all negative emotions (such as anger, fear, sadness, jealousy, envy, impatience) base on the same emotion: an unpleasant inner uneasiness, the UE, which can be felt in the gut. Similarly, all positive emotions (such as joy, pride, thankfulness) base on the same emotion: a pleasant feeling, the GE, which can be felt in the head. With respect to his or her bodily experience, a human feels primarily two different feelings when (cognitively induced) emotions appear: an unpleasant one (the UE) or a pleasant one (the GE). The sometimes described multitude of emotions thus refers less to a multitude of feelings that are bodily experienced in various ways but to a multitude of situations in which the two elementary emotions (UE, GE) occur. Occasionally the elementary emotions are accompanied by other feelings (e.g. a trembling). For example, a person can get a red (hot) head in case of anger. However, not any anger leads to this secondary symptom in such an individual, similarly as not any worry inevitably leads to a fearful facial expression. Always however the UE appears in case of an anger or a worry.

The elementary emotions are automatically activated in the individual by appropriate detectors. The latter are on the one hand specialized physical detectors (e.g. in case of hunger) and on the other hand logical detectors. Eight different logical detectors can be distinguished. According to clearly defined criteria they activate the unpleasant and bothering elementary emotion UE in situations which are adverse or potentially unfavourable for the individual. Similarly, eight logical detectors activate the pleasant elementary emotion GE in case of actually or potentially favourable situations. Those cognitive impulses shape the negative and positive emotions (e.g. jealousy, elevation, nostalgia, frustration).

The knowledge of the function of cognitive impulses (or of the underlying logical detectors) enables the individual to analyse appearing emotions more precisely and to react more competent in critical situations. With the aid of the model presented here, emotions can be named more clearly and understood better. In case of jealousy for example it becomes apparent which aspects are primarily responsible for the inner uneasiness in the individual –

be it the possible loss of the partner, its disrespectful behaviour, the role or the advantages of the rival, or the possible reaction of common friends. This can't be derived from the general term "jealousy". The understanding of emotions is also important because they influence the decision making of the individual. Furthermore, inter-human behaviour based on emotions can be explained better with the model. However, it is crucial that the individual pays attention to the contents of automatic thoughts and to the prevailing circumstances at the time when a cognitive impulse occurs. The corresponding cognitions are key to understand which detector is active at the moment. Emotions can only fully be understood together with the accompanying cognitions.

The activation of cognitive impulses and thus of emotions follows remarkably simple and clear rules. Saved information (e.g. about the resources of the individual, its goals) is connected with the current perceptions of the individual. Although simple, the activation rules can lead to complex appearing behaviour. Most of the processes involved work automatically, i.e. without voluntary assistance of the individual.

Also from an evolutionary point of view cognitive impulses can be explained well. They are independent of the composition of the available senses (or receptors) of an individual. Moreover, the effects of cognitive impulses can be observed at animals of many other species. That means that in similar emotional situations animals show similar reactions like humans. Nature has hold the structure of the cognitive impulses (as described in their definitions) flexible what makes them universally effective, independently of the concrete composition of the environment or of the individual. There are indications that cognitive impulses could (in a functional respect, not in the form of emotions like in humans) already exist in biological cells in the cascades of molecular signals. The UE would then be represented by one or several leading signals. In that respect, cognitive impulses possibly form a fundamental basic structure for self-organized systems of all kind.

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